

APPENDIX B: LIST OF PRIMARY STUDIES INCLUDED IN THIS SLR

- R1. Angeletti, F., Chatzigiannakis, I., & Vitaletti, A. (2017, November). Privacy preserving data management in recruiting participants for digital clinical trials. In Proceedings of the first international workshop on human-centered sensing, networking, and systems (pp. 7-12).
- R2. Kim, M. G., Lee, A. R., Kwon, H. J., Kim, J. W., & Kim, I. K. (2018, December). Sharing medical questionnaires based on blockchain. In 2018 IEEE International Conference on Bioinformatics and Biomedicine (BIBM) (pp. 2767-2769). IEEE.
- R3. Mamoshina, P., Ojomoko, L., Yanovich, Y., Ostrovski, A., Botezatu, A., Prikhodko, P., ... & Zhavoronkov, A. (2018). Converging blockchain and next-generation artificial intelligence technologies to decentralize and accelerate biomedical research and healthcare. *Oncotarget*, 9(5), 5665.
- R4. Angeletti, F., Chatzigiannakis, I., & Vitaletti, A. (2018). Towards an architecture to guarantee both data privacy and utility in the first phases of digital clinical trials. *Sensors*, 18(12), 4175.
- R5. Maslove, D. M., Klein, J., Brohman, K., & Martin, P. (2018). Using blockchain technology to manage clinical trials data: a proof-of-concept study. *JMIR medical informatics*, 6(4), e11949.
- R6. Zhuang, Y., Sheets, L., Shae, Z., Tsai, J. J., & Shyu, C. R. (2018). Applying blockchain technology for health information exchange and persistent monitoring for clinical trials. In AMIA Annual Symposium Proceedings (Vol. 2018, p. 1167). American Medical Informatics Association.
- R7. Mann, S. P., Savulescu, J., Ravaud, P., & Benchoufi, M. (2021). Blockchain, consent and present for medical research. *Journal of medical ethics*, 47(4), 244-250.
- R8. Qi, Z., Shulin, Y., & Ruoyu, R. (2019, September). Application of Block Chain in Digital Copyright Protection. In Proceedings of the 2019 2nd International Conference on Information Hiding and Image Processing (pp. 5-9).
- R9. Bernardi, F. A., Lima, V., Pellison, F., de Azevedo Marques, P. M., Rijo, R., Galliez, R. M., ... & Alves, D. (2019, July). Blockchain Based Network for Tuberculosis: A Data Sharing Initiative in Brazil. In ICIMTH (pp. 264-267).
- R10. Charles, W., Marler, N., Long, L., & Manion, S. (2019). Blockchain compliance by design: Regulatory considerations for blockchain in clinical research. *Frontiers in Blockchain*, 2, 18.
- R11. Minssen, T., Rajam, N., & Bogers, M. (2020). Clinical trial data transparency and GDPR compliance: Implications for data sharing and open innovation. *Science and Public Policy*, 47(5), 616-626.
- R12. Carlini, F., Carlini, R., Dalla Palma, S., Pareschi, R., & Zappone, F. (2020). The Genesy model for a blockchain-based fair ecosystem of genomic data. *Frontiers in Blockchain*, 3, 483227.
- R13. Ghaffaripour, S., & Miri, A. (2020, October). A decentralized, privacy-preserving and crowdsourcing-based approach to medical research. In 2020 IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC) (pp. 4510-4515). IEEE.
- R14. Sung, M., Park, S., Jung, S., Lee, E., Lee, J., & Park, Y. R. (2020). Developing a mobile app for monitoring medical record changes using blockchain: development and usability study. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 22(8), e19657.
- R15. Mamo, N., Martin, G. M., Desira, M., Ellul, B., & Ebejer, J. P. (2020). Dwarna: a blockchain solution for dynamic consent in biobanking. *European Journal of Human Genetics*, 28(5), 609-626.
- R16. Witowski, J., Choi, J., Jeon, S., Kim, D., Chung, J., Conklin, J., ... & Do, S. (2021). MarkIt: a collaborative artificial intelligence annotation platform leveraging blockchain for medical imaging research. *Blockchain in Healthcare Today*, 4.
- R17. Li, M. M., & Kuo, T. T. (2021). Previewable contract-based on-chain X-ray image sharing framework for clinical research. *International journal of medical informatics*, 156, 104599.
- R18. Badulescu, Y., & Cheikhrouhou, N. (2021, August). A framework integrating internet of things and blockchain in clinical trials reverse supply chain. In IFIP International Conference on Advances in Production Management Systems (pp. 98-106). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- R19. Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., & Riccio, E. (2021, May). A novel architecture for enhancing Electronic Health Record interoperability: A Blockchain-based approach. In 2021 IEEE Technology & Engineering Management Conference-Europe (TEMSCON-EUR) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.
- R20. Hang, L., Kim, B., Kim, K., & Kim, D. (2021). A permissioned blockchain-based clinical trial service platform to improve trial data transparency. *BioMed research international*, 2021.
- R21. Nourani, A., Ayatollahi, H., & Solaymani-Dodaran, M. (2022). A clinical data management system for diabetes clinical trials. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*, 2022.

- R22. Vazquez, P., Hirayama-Shoji, K., Novik, S., Krauss, S., & Rayner, S. (2022). Globally Accessible Distributed Data Sharing (GADDS): a decentralized FAIR platform to facilitate data sharing in the life sciences. *Bioinformatics*, 38(15), 3812-3817.
- R23. Hu, C., Li, C., Zhang, G., Lei, Z., Shah, M., Zhang, Y., ... & Bao, R. (2022). CrowdMed-II: a blockchain-based framework for efficient consent management in health data sharing. *World Wide Web*, 25(3), 1489-1515.
- R24. Zhuang, Y., Zhang, L., Gao, X., Shae, Z. Y., Tsai, J. J., Li, P., & Shyu, C. R. (2022). Re-Engineering a clinical trial management system using blockchain technology: system design, development, and case studies. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 24(6), e36774.
- R25. Kang, G., & Kim, Y. G. (2022). Secure collaborative platform for health care research in an open environment: perspective on accountability in access control. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 24(10), e37978.
- R26. Gürsoy, G., Brannon, C. M., Ni, E., Wagner, S., Khanna, A., & Gerstein, M. (2022). Storing and analyzing a genome on a blockchain. *Genome biology*, 23(1), 134.
- R27. Oakley, J., Worley, C., Yu, L., Brooks, R. R., Özçelik, İ. L. K. E. R., Skjellum, A., & Obeid, J. S. (2023). Scribe: A Secure Audit Trail for Clinical Trial Data Fusion. *Digital threats: research and practice*, 4(2), 1-20.
- R28. Kalita, K. P., Chettri, S. K., & Deka, R. K. (2023, January). A Blockchain-based Model for Maternal Health Information Exchange and Prediction of Health Risks using Machine Learning. In *2023 International Conference on Intelligent and Innovative Technologies in Computing, Electrical and Electronics (IITCEE)* (pp. 1184-1189). IEEE.
- R29. Hang, L., Ullah, I., Yang, J., & Chen, C. (2023). An improved Kalman filter using ANN-based learning module to predict transaction throughput of blockchain network in clinical trials. *Peer-to-Peer Networking and Applications*, 16(2), 520-537.
- R30. Wang, H., Zhang, X., Xia, Y., & Wu, X. (2023). An intelligent blockchain-based access control framework with federated learning for genome-wide association studies. *Computer Standards & Interfaces*, 84, 103694.
- R31. Jaberansary, M., Maia, M., Ucer Yediell, Y., Beyan, O., & Kirsten, T. (2023, April). Analyzing Distributed Medical Data in FAIR Data Spaces. In *Companion Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023* (pp. 1480-1484).
- R32. Al Amin, M., Altarawneh, A., & Ray, I. (2023). Informed consent as patient driven policy for clinical diagnosis and treatment: A smart contract based approach. In *Proceedings of the 20th International Conference on Security and Cryptography-SECURITY* (pp. 159-170).
- R33. Kuo, T. T., & Pham, A. (2023). Quorum-based model learning on a blockchain hierarchical clinical research network using smart contracts. *International journal of medical informatics*, 169, 104924.
- R34. Barbaria, S., Mahjoubi, H., & Rahmouni, H. B. (2023). A novel blockchain-based architectural modal for healthcare data integrity: Covid19 screening laboratory use-case. *Procedia Computer Science*, 219, 1436-1443.